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“STRONG AND INDEPENDENT”

Only you know who is truly superior to everyone else. Everyone who knows you well has a lot to say about you, but only you fully understand who you are. Often, describing someone or expressing an opinion is straightforward. Many students find it difficult to describe themselves. They have difficulty deciding what to include and what to leave out. To address this issue, we will be discussing numerous articles about me today. I'm a bright, extroverted woman with a great sense of humor. It's important to understand that, despite the fact that I first come off as a very quiet, independent lady, once I get to know people and start to feel comfortable in my surroundings, I am really very good. Although it's hard for me to make friends, they are fantastic once I do since we are all so different. I always feel gratified when people laugh and love my jokes and humor.

I am a very compassionate, kind, and sensitive girl, as my close friends will confirm. I'm soft on the inside yet have a harsh exterior. Furthermore, when it comes to right and wrong, I am a person with strong morals and values. My feeling of straightness and honesty is also quite strong. Although I am aware that we all occasionally put up a front and conceal our genuine feelings, there are certain individuals who do this on a regular basis, and I can't bear them.